

Deliverable 9.2

Full Communication Toolkit

Version 1

WP 9
Deliverable 9.2
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Executive Summary

This report provides an overview of the **MISSION ATLANTIC Communications Toolkit**. It outlines the resources available at M18 (February 2022), their development, where they can be found and how they can be used by project partners to facilitate effective communication and raise widespread awareness of the project.

The toolkit of communication resources includes: the project **logo**, brand and associated **style (brand) guidelines**, presentation **templates**, public project **website**, promotional **factsheets**, **posters**, **infographics** and **slide deck**. Additional tools include the project newsletter, videos and animations within, press releases and project social media channels. MISSION ATLANTIC's communication activities will run for the full duration of the project and further resources will be developed to further support partners with communication activities.

All elements scheduled to be developed by M18 (February 2022) have been achieved before this due date. All tools and materials will be maintained and updated as necessary, and further resources developed over the course of the project in line with the project's Description of Action, as well as in response to project results and stakeholder requirements.

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MISSION ATLANTIC Background

MISSION ATLANTIC develops and systematically applies Integrated Ecosystem Assessments (IEAs) in the Atlantic Ocean. IEAs enable identification of ecosystem components most at risk from natural hazards and the consequences of human activities. The project employs all available information on those sources, the pressures they impose and the ecosystem components that are affected, to identify the most important risk factors for sustainable development of the Atlantic Ocean. MISSION ATLANTIC develops and tests high-resolution numerical ocean ecosystem models, as well as employing advanced statistical approaches, artificial neural networks, and risk assessment methods in support of the IEA cycle. Cross-Atlantic seagoing activities will collect new observations on the shelf and open ocean, across benthic and pelagic biomes, to validate ecosystem models and explore the biogeography of plankton and fish communities. Advanced combinations of marine robotic solutions and acoustic sensors are further developed and deployed to provide new data and to deliver the next generation of autonomous systems in support of IEAs.

MISSION ATLANTIC aims at supporting all Atlantic Ocean research alliance and the implementation of the Galway and Belem statements. In 2017, the European Union, South Africa and Brazil co-signed the [Belém statement](#) on Atlantic Research and Innovation Cooperation for the South and tropical Atlantic and Southern Ocean. Following the Galway Statement, which focuses on North-Atlantic cooperation, the Belém statement furthers the integrated approach to research and development across the whole Atlantic Ocean and its bordering countries

The role of this deliverable

This report provides an overview of the MISSION ATLANTIC Communications Toolkit. It describes the resources developed, outlines where the resources can be found and how they can be used by project partners to facilitate effective communication and raise widespread awareness of the project.

Contributors to this deliverable

This deliverable was written by ERINN Innovation.

Acronyms and Abbreviations

CS	Case Study(ies)
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package(s)

1. Introduction

The **MISSION ATLANTIC Communications Toolkit** has been developed to support effective communication and widespread awareness of the project, its objectives, results and activities amongst stakeholders.

The toolkit is intended to help partners, and case study leaders, to promote the project, communicate the project's objectives, disseminate its findings, and engage stakeholders, including the public, in project results and activities in an efficient and consistent manner. The resources developed have been designed to facilitate communication activities carried out by the full partnership for the duration of the project.

Developing the MISSION ATLANTIC Communication Toolkit began with designing a strong project brand to establish project recognition. ERINN Innovation (WP9 co-lead) developed the project **brand**, and from this, further developed a project **logo** and accompanying **style (brand) guidelines**, different **templates** for a variety of presentation forms (oral presentation, poster presentation and reports), the project **website**, project **factsheets**, **posters** and **infographics** (graphics and icons) and **slide deck**.

Additional communication resources including an **e-newsletter**, with **short videos** and animations, a **press release** promoting the project kick-off, and dedicated **social media channels** (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube) have been developed by WP9 leads (UPO & ERINN Innovation) together with input from project partners.

Further resources, including additional videos (linked to technical outputs, e-learning and training in WP8), blogs, participation in events and ocean literacy initiatives by project partners are foreseen in the second period of the project. Other communication elements such as updating the website and social media, additional e-newsletters, press releases and promotional articles, blogs, and participation in events and ocean literacy initiatives will be on-going activities until the end of the project.

The MISSION ATLANTIC communication resources are available to download from the MISSION ATLANTIC Teams ([WP9 > D9.2 - COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT](#)) and can be requested from WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

2. Project Brand

2.1. Project logo

The project logo is an integral part of the brand as it is included on all project promotional material. The MISSION ATLANTIC logo is constructed using a combination of rounded bold lettering, harmonious colours and illustration signifying the key focus of the project – sustainable development of the Atlantic Ocean. Three abstract dolphin shapes convey sustainability and are crafted in the form of a sustainability icon. Inside, the Atlantic Ocean is shown in a face on view of the globe, to represent ‘our ocean’. The colours are fresh and bright signifying the MISSION ATLANTIC vision for safeguarding marine biodiversity for future generations.

Figure 1 MISSION ATLANTIC logo options in full colour and black and white

The MISSION ATLANTIC logo suite includes the primary project logo in full colour and mono colour (black and white); a horizontal version; the icon; and a combined EU emblem and disclaimer graphic (including the Grant Agreement number). Guidance on how to properly utilise the MISSION ATLANTIC logo can be found in the Brand Guidelines (Annex 1).

The MISSION ATLANTIC suite of logos is available on the MISSION ATLANTIC Teams channel ([WP9 > D9.2 - COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT > LOGO SUITE](#)) and can be requested from WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

2.2. Style Guidelines

The MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines (Annex 1) offer the means by which all partners in MISSION ATLANTIC can achieve the prescribed standards of presentation. The document includes information on the different versions of the project logo (typeface, colour palette, and their correct use), guidelines for using the PowerPoint and Poster templates, and details on the correct EU acknowledgement that must be included with all dissemination activities related to the project. The brand guidelines will be updated if needed over the course of the project.

The MISSION ATLANTIC brand guidelines are available on the MISSION ATLANTIC Teams ([WP9 > D9.2 - COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT>BRAND GUIDE](#)) and can be requested from WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

3. Presentation Templates

All MISSION ATLANTIC presentation templates are available on the MISSION ATLANTIC Teams ([WP9 > D9.2 - COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT>Templates](#)) and can be requested from WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu). Font typeface, size, style, colour use and other presentation guidelines can be found in the MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines (Annex 1). These templates will be updated as required over the course of the project.

If partners wish to make changes, have suggestions for updates or other requirements for any of the templates (e.g., other dimensions for print posters), they should contact WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

3.1. Oral Presentation Template (PowerPoint)

A MISSION ATLANTIC PowerPoint template has been developed to use at internal and external events when presenting the project and/or its outcomes (see Brand Guidelines p15). It is available in both normal and widescreen format. The template includes a cover slide (see below) where to include the title of presentation and the speaker, two main body slides (with and without the MISSION ATLANTIC icon) and a closing side containing relevant contact details with the project.

Figure 2 MISSION ATLANTIC oral presentation template

3.2. Poster Presentation Template (PowerPoint)

A MISSION ATLANTIC poster template has been designed and developed for any poster presentations on the project and/or its outcomes. The poster is designed for printing on A0 paper in full colour. To accommodate space requirements for scientific poster presentations, options have been provided where the poster background can include or exclude the leaf icon and project tagline.

Figure 3 MISSION ATLANTIC poster presentation template

3.3. Deliverable Report Template (Word)

A Word template has been designed and developed for MISSION ATLANTIC project deliverables, as well as internal and external reports. The template includes the MISSION ATLANTIC branding and style set up with headings, formatting, font type, size and colours.

Figure 4 MISSION ATLANTIC deliverable report template

4. Project Website

The project website (missionatlantic.eu/) is a key communication tool for promoting the project to a wide audience, disseminating the project's objectives, work plan and results to all possible end-users, and for supporting IEA operations, case study and stakeholder interactions.

The MISSION ATLANTIC website has been developed following the EU's best practice guidelines¹ for project websites. The website is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a privacy statement and cookie bar informing website visitors about what MISSION ATLANTIC does with any personal data gathered. Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website.

To ensure successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated with new information throughout the project's lifetime. The website will remain active for five years after the end of the project, to serve as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and for promoting the outputs of publicly funded research in the domain beyond the project's lifetime.

The website plays multiple roles:

- A communication tool to **promote the project**, its objectives, the consortium partnership, funding, project activities and results in research, industry, policy and public arenas
- A dissemination channel to **showcase results**, key outcomes and major achievements and keep update interested parties on project progress
- A **news portal** and communication resource for project news, notices, press releases, events, media resources and updates from MISSION ATLANTIC and associated projects
- A **repository** for public deliverables and outputs (data, reports and publications)
- A **platform** for case study and stakeholder interactions and to run models and tools developed in the project (e.g., StrathE2E)

The website uses a hub-and-spoke model to organise the content. The structure follows an easy to use and intuitive pathway that allows the user to explore the website easily. The top menu bar, visible on all pages, contains buttons for sections of the website on 'Overview', 'About', 'Case Studies', 'Team', 'News & Events', 'Results', and 'Resources' direct links to the partners area (Teams channel and project intranet managed by DTU), a 'subscribe to news' button and 'search' function. The bottom banner, visible on all pages, contains contact information, the EU emblem, disclaimer and acknowledgment of funding, links to the data policy and privacy statement. It also includes direct links to all the MISSION ATLANTIC social media channels (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube).

Snapshots of the website can be seen in the figures below.

¹ http://www.eurosfair.prdd.fr/7pc/documents/1271333123_project_website_guidelines_en.pdf

By studying the complexity of Atlantic Ocean ecosystems, maritime culture, traditions and sustainable management, MISSION ATLANTIC will contribute to better and more sustainable future for life on earth.

MISSION ATLANTIC will be the first initiative to develop operational IEAs and systematically apply IEAs through the Atlantic basin and regional case studies.

5 Steps in the IEA Process

Figure 5 MISSION ATLANTIC website screenshots

5. Project Factsheets

A project factsheet was designed to give the general audience an overview of the MISSION ATLANTIC project. It describes the project, its main objectives, methodology, expected impacts, and the consortium, and will be used to raise general awareness of the project. The factsheet is a full colour double sided A4 leaflet. The factsheet format was chosen for ease of use by all partners. Both web and professional printer versions available. The web version can be viewed online and used for ‘in-house’ printing. When printing in-house, partners are advised to use 160 – 180 gsm paper.

The project factsheet is available in all languages commonly used at the case study sites, including **Danish, English, French, German, Norwegian, Portuguese (Brazilian and Portuguese), and Spanish.**

Case Study leaders and partners are encouraged to distribute the factsheet through their networks and at relevant events. If partners wish to have the factsheet available in another language, they should contact WP9 co-lead WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

The MISSION ATLANTIC factsheets (all languages) are available on the MISSION ATLANTIC Teams ([WP9 > D9.2 - COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT>PROJECT FACTSHEET](#)), the MISSION ATLANTIC website (under resources) and can be requested from WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

Figure 6 MISSION ATLANTIC factsheet (English)

6. Posters and Infographics

A selection of graphics, icons and posters have been designed and developed to represent MISSION ATLANTIC’s approach and project design, the project objectives, seven case studies, and the project’s Integrated Ecosystem Assessment (IEA).

An **infographic** explaining MISSION ATLANTIC’s IEA has been designed to give a general audience an overview of the IEA framework, cycle and expected outcome. The infographic is a full colour (800 x2000 px) image and is available in several lay outs and dimensions for use in a variety of formats (e.g., A4 reports, presentation, social media cards). The IEA infographic is also available as a **poster**, as is the project factsheet (see section 4).

The infographic pack, including all icons, graphics and the IEA infographics, is available to download the MISSION ATLANTIC Teams Channel ([WP9 > D9.2 - COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT>INFOGRAPHICS](#)) and can be requested from WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

Figure 7 MISSION ATLANTIC IEA infographic and poster

7. Slide Deck

A general **slide deck** (standard 4:3 and widescreen 16:9) providing an overview of the project has also been developed (see below). This can be used by all partners to introduce the project objectives, methodology, and key outputs. The MISSION ATLANTIC slide deck will be updated as required over the course of the project.

The slide deck is available to download the MISSION ATLANTIC Teams Channel ([WP9 > D9.2 - COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT>SLIDEDECK](#)) and can be requested from WP9 co-leader ERINN (annette@erinn.eu).

Project Concept

- MISSION ATLANTIC will better our understanding of Atlantic Ocean ecosystems by taking a fully holistic and integrative approach to assess the current and future state of the whole Atlantic Ocean: *no pressure or ecosystem component will be excluded.*
- Using ecosystem-based management approaches and an Integrated Ecosystems Assessment (IEA) Framework, MISSION ATLANTIC will synthesise the necessary knowledge and provide tools to support marine resource managers and policy makers to move towards a positive future for the Atlantic Ocean.

Project Objectives

- Assess** the status of ecosystems in the Atlantic Ocean and their resilience to the impact of pressures, including food provision, climate regulation and cultural services.
- Map** the present and establish the future 3D distributions of Atlantic biomes and their pressures to support the sustainable use of marine resources.
- Develop** new indicators, tools and technologies to identify risks to, and vulnerabilities of, the Atlantic Ocean under different climate conditions and management scenarios.
- Formulate and transfer** assessment guidelines, data, and modelling tools into ecosystem-based management procedures to support sustainable governance of marine resources and the development of the Blue Economy.
- Educate** ocean resource managers and researchers in the application of the IEA Framework within countries bordering the North, South and Tropical Atlantic Ocean.

The Challenge

- The sustainable management of our ocean resources is dependant on our ability to assess and predict drivers of change and their subsequent impact on marine ecosystems.
- However, drivers of change are extremely variable, subject to large uncertainties and have complex interconnections, making them difficult to assess.
- MISSION ATLANTIC will combine all available environmental and socioecological data from different scales and sectors and, in consultation with stakeholders, apply a flexible IEA process.
- The results will provide a comprehensive view of the entire Atlantic Ocean system and identify the most important factors influencing sustainable development.

Case Studies

MISSION ATLANTIC will develop and systematically apply IEA at seven regional Case Studies, with contrasting biogeography in sub-Arctic and Tropical regions of the Atlantic Ocean, ranging from shelf seas to the mid-Atlantic Ridge.

The project will advance the Operational Readiness Level (ORL) of each regional IEA, and by synthesising the results, develop an operational IEA for the entire Atlantic basin (ORL 1 → ORL 5).

Case Studies
1. Norwegian Sea
2. North Mid Atlantic Ridge
3. Celtic Sea
4. Canary Current
5. South Mid Atlantic Ridge
6. South Brazilian Shelf
7. Benguela Current

Figure 8 MISSION ATLANTIC slide deck

8. Newsletters

Digital newsletters will be distributed, twice per year to the project mailing list, as part of the MISSION ATLANTIC communication strategy. The newsletters will be designed, following the project brand guide, and will include images, short videos and animations links and interactive articles that report on the scientific project activities in an accessible format for general audiences.

The MISSION ATLANTIC e-newsletters will be made available under the ‘Resources’ page (filter ‘e-newsletter’) on the project website.

Figure 9 MISSION ATLANTIC e-newsletter, issue 1 (October 2021), screen shots

9. Press Releases and Promotional Articles

The first press release, following the MISSION ATLANTIC project kick-off meeting, was published on 30th September 2020. The press release was widely distributed through Cordis, Twitter, as well as the consortium’s and ERINN Innovation’s networks (approved GDPR mailing lists and related project networks). The press release is available from the project website on the Resources page. Further press releases and promotional articles will be produced when major project outcomes become available and will then be distributed widely.

Figure 10 MISSION ATLANTIC press release

10. Social Media Channels

Social networking is an integral part of the MISSION ATLANTIC communication strategy. Dedicated social media accounts have been established for the project and are actively maintained by WP9 leader UPO, with support from ERINN Innovation. All posts are in accordance with the H2020 Programme Guidance Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects.

- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/missionatlantic>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/69560432/admin/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/MISSIONATLANTIC/>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCf4jKwIPPO51BDG5peqNzhg>

11. Conclusion

The aim of this deliverable D9.2 was to develop a range of strong communication tools and resources to raise widespread awareness of the project and its results amongst stakeholders. This report outlines the resources available at M18 (February 2022). The toolkit of communication resources includes: project logo, brand and associated style guidelines, promotional factsheet, presentation templates, public project website, infographics (graphics and icons), posters and slide deck. Additional resources including the newsletter, videos and animations within, press releases and project social media channels, have been developed and are described here. MISSION ATLANTIC's communication activities will run for the full duration of the project and further resources will be developed to further support partners with communication activities.

Annex 1 – Brand Guidelines

Towards the Sustainable Development of the Atlantic Ocean: Mapping and assessing the present and future status of Atlantic marine ecosystems under the influence of climate change and exploitation

A large, stylized version of the logo graphic, featuring a central globe surrounded by three curved arrows in orange, green, and blue, all rendered in a flat, vector style.

BRAND GUIDELINES

 @MISSIONATLANTIC

www.missionatlantic.eu

MISSION ATLANTIC
Brand Guidelines

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3 MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines

INTRODUCTION

Brand guidelines

The brand guidelines set out in this manual for **MISSION ATLANTIC** offer the means by which all partners can achieve the prescribed standards of presentation related to the **MISSION ATLANTIC** project.

It is recommended that partners follow this manual to ensure a high standard of project presentation in all **MISSION ATLANTIC** dissemination activities.

For any queries regarding the implementation of the **MISSION ATLANTIC** brand guidelines, please contact Annette Wilson, Intrigo Ltd (annette@intrigo.eu).

www.missionatlantic.eu

4 MISSION ATLANTIC
Brand Guidelines

LOGO

5 MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines

LOGO

The **MISSION ATLANTIC** logo is constructed using a combination of rounded bold lettering, harmonious colour choices and illustration.

This section gives you guidelines on how to use the logo in any format, for example the recommended type face to use, the colour palette and best use of the logo on different backgrounds.

When using the logo, the full project name should be visible, where possible, elsewhere in the dissemination activity.

Colour Logo

6 **MISSION ATLANTIC**
Brand Guidelines

ONE COLOUR LOGO

The one colour version logos are intended for applications that are restricted in colour, such as fax, memo etc. or any time it is not possible to use colour printing techniques.

Black logo

White logo

7 MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines

CORRECT USE OF LOGO

Colour background variations

The preferred background for the **MISSION ATLANTIC** logo is white, but there will be some instances where the logo needs to be used over a colour other than white. In this case, you may have to use either the white or black version of the logo.

Whether the logo is being used in full colour, black or white, please ensure that the logo is always legible and there is sufficient contrast between all the elements.

Correct

The full colour logo is only fully visible on a light background.

Incorrect

The full colour logo is not fully visible on a background similar in colour to the logo itself.

Correct

The white logo is only fully visible on a dark background.

Incorrect

The black logo is not fully visible on a dark background.

Correct

The black logo is only fully visible on a light background.

Incorrect

The white logo is not fully visible on a light background.

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Brand Guidelines**

CORRECT USE OF LOGO (CTD.)

Photographic background variations

The preferred background for the **MISSION ATLANTIC** logo is white, but in some cases it is necessary to use the logo over images. In all cases, it is important to ensure that all elements of the logo are clearly visible.

Correct

The full colour logo is fully visible on a light image.

Incorrect

The full colour logo is not fully visible on an image similar in colour to the logo.

Correct

The white logo is fully visible on a dark image.

Incorrect

The black logo is not fully visible on a dark image.

Correct

The black logo is fully visible on a light image.

Incorrect

The white logo is not fully visible on a light image.

**9 MISSION ATLANTIC
Brand Guidelines**

CORRECT USE OF LOGO (CTD.)

Clearance space

Clearance space is the area surrounding the logo that should be kept free of other graphical elements. You should allow sufficient space around the logo.

The minimum required space to use around the logo is the height/width of the "M" from the logotype.

Clearance space for logo

10 MISSION ATLANTIC
Brand Guidelines

CORRECT USE OF LOGO (CTD.)

Minimum size

The **MISSION ATLANTIC** logo can be increased to any size you require however the minimum size the logo should be displayed at only at 55mm in width. Where possible, the logo should not be used below these sizes as legibility will be compromised.

Minimum size
= 55mm width

11 MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines

INCORRECT USE OF LOGO

What not to do

Never recreate elements of the artwork. Do not modify elements or alter colours. Please adhere to the guidelines below.

X Do not distort logo

X Do not modify colours

X Do not rearrange elements

X Do not add elements

X Do not distort the icon

X Do not modify proportion

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TYPEFACES

Primary – Gilroy (Graphic Design Use Only)

Gilroy is the primary **MISSION ATLANTIC** typeface. This simple, modern font helps communicate ideas clearly and confidently. It is highly legible in both print and digital communications. It is available in a range of weights: from light to bold.

Gilroy is primarily used for print design.

Secondary – Calibri (General Use)

Calibri is the secondary **MISSION ATLANTIC** typeface. Calibri reflects the clean look of the primary typeface and should be used whenever possible within Microsoft Office applications i.e. Word, Powerpoint, Excel etc.

Calibri Regular can be used for all standard communication materials e.g. letters/faxes/reports/emails etc.

Calibri is packaged with all Microsoft and Macintosh computers.

Gilroy Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Gilroy Extra Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Calibri Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Calibri Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

0123456789 @*?!&%+="

13 MISSION ATLANTIC
Brand Guidelines

COLOUR PALETTE

Print

The CMYK values are required when preparing materials for professional print jobs.

In-office printing will provide varied results depending on equipment and as a result, 100% colour accuracy cannot be expected.

Web

The RGB values are required when preparing materials for the web.

It is important to note that the calibration of monitors, desktop printers and projection equipment can vary. Please adhere to the RGB values provided to ensure consistency across all materials for the web.

Mission Atlantic Blue

C 97	
M 81	R 33
Y 10	G 75
K 2	B 146

Mission Atlantic Green

C 47	
M 5	R 140
Y 50	G 195
K 0	B 152

Mission Atlantic Light Orange

C 1	
M 24	R 250
Y 53	G 198
K 0	B 133

Mission Atlantic Light Blue

C 45	
M 20	R 136
Y 0	G 178
K 0	B 233

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Brand Guidelines

APPLICATION

15 MISSION ATLANTIC
Brand Guidelines

POWERPOINT PRESENTATION

Cover, context & closing slides

Please follow the PowerPoint template where possible. The recommended font is Calibri. We suggest using 18-20pt for the body font size, 28pt for subheadings and 36pt for headings in the content slides to ensure that the text is legible.

Title slide layout

Content slide layouts

Closing slide layout

16 MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines

POWERPOINT POSTER

Please follow the PowerPoint template where possible. It is A0 in size. The recommended font is Calibri. There are options for a poster background with or without the icon.

Poster background layouts

18 MISSION ATLANTIC Brand Guidelines

Acknowledgement of EU funding

All publications or any other dissemination relating to results should include the EU emblem and the following statement to indicate that said results were generated with the assistance of financial support from the EU:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 862428 (MISSION ATLANTIC). This output reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency (REA) cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

A combined EU emblem and disclaimer graphic is available in the **MISSION ATLANTIC** logo suite.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 862428 (MISSION ATLANTIC). This output reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency (REA) cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

EU emblem

High-resolution versions of the emblem can be found here: <http://europa.eu/about-eu/basicinformation/symbols/flag/>

 @MISSIONATLANTIC

www.missionatlantic.eu

Designed and
developed by
Intrigo Ltd

Document Information

EU Project	No 862428	Acronym	MISSION ATLANTIC
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Project website	www.missionatlantic.eu		

Deliverable	N°	D9.2	Title	Full Communication Toolkit
Work Package	N°	9	Title	Societal Engagement & Communication
Work Package Leader	Lead: UPO Co-lead: ERINN Innovation			
Work Participants	DTU, UHAM, AZTI, IMR, MBA, PML, CLS, STRATH, NOC, IFREMER, PLOCAN, IMAR, UCT, UFSC, MI, IEO, SSBE, USP, ICES, SANBI, AIRC, WMU, CS Leader partners: IMR, IMAR, UCT, UFSC, MI, IEO, USP.			

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